

Metadata description for field work material

Title: Field Work on the EUTF for Africa in Ethiopia: Interviews and Observations

Description: Interviews with various stakeholders working on or otherwise involved in two different projects funded through the EU Emergency Trust Fund for Africa (2015-2025) in Addis Ababa and Gambella, Ethiopia ($N = 22$). The data includes interviews from stakeholders from multiple NGO's, the Delegation of the European Union to Ethiopia, and secondary stakeholders (health officials). The data is also inclusive of a field diary, containing notes on my own (participant) observations and other information collected as part of informal conversations.

Keywords: Africa, Ethiopia, EUTF for Africa, migration, development cooperation

Date of data collection: The data was collected in March-April 2023 and May 2024.

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Preservation of Research Data: The data is stored in a password-protected university OneDrive folder.